

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

The European Protest and Coercion dataset lists daily and sub-daily data on protest and coercion events across 28 European countries from 1980 to 1995. It was developed by Prof Ron Francisco and supported by both the National Science Foundation as well as the Department of Political Science and the General Research Fund of the University of Kansas. The data is available as separate datasets for each country. This data review will focus on the German Democratic Republic (GDR) dataset which lists 1.100+ entries in the time period from January 1st 1980 to October 3rd 1990. As of summer 2024, the data collection seems to have concluded (1). The data review contains a link leading to the official Protest and Coercion Data website from which both the dataset and additional information in the form of a codebook are available as a free download.

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Data Review - Protest And Coercion Data

The European Protest and Coercion dataset lists daily and sub-daily data on protest and coercion events across 28 European countries from 1980 to 1995. It was developed by Prof Ron Francisco and supported by both the National Science Foundation as well as the Department of Political Science and the General Research Fund of the University of Kansas. The data is available as separate datasets for each country. This data review will focus on the German Democratic Republic (GDR) dataset which lists 1.100+ entries. As of summer 2024, the data collection seems to have concluded (1).

The European Protest and Coercion dataset gathered its data from Reuters Textline library which is accessible via Lexis-Nexis. This library provided a total of over 400 publications, including global, regional and local wire-services as well as online newspapers and magazines. Depending on the country in question additional sources might have been utilised. If that was the case these sources are listed in the codebook for each country (2).

If two or more reports addressing the same event mention conflicting information, the research team decided on prioritising the information of the highest quality source. If however multiple high quality sources still include conflicting information the research team determined the mean to use in the data. The source listed within the dataset is the first encountered report that lists the event, meaning not all information listed in the data might be available from the cited report, since some of it might only have become apparent through analysing later reports. Thus, the research team states: "Anyone who seeks to find more information on any event therefore should check not only the cited source and date, but then go to later reports in Reuters Textline." (2).

The dataset includes all reported protest and repressive events, as well as economic conflicts related to politics, reported in the time period from January 1st 1980 to October 3rd 1990. This timeframe is shorter than those of the other datasets since the GDR ceased to exist in this form on October 2nd 1990. There were no limitations for inclusion other than information on the day and location a given event occurred. For events that spanned over multiple days each day was coded as a separate event. Generally, only one coder, with significant background knowledge of the given country, was responsible for coding per country since context is often valuable for making decisions while coding. On top of that two methods of machine-assisted coding were used to facilitate the coding process. Most coders utilised the KEDS software to code data and then transferred this machine-assisted data onto an Excel spreadsheet, which was the primary coding document (2).

The following variables were included in the coding process:

- „A. Event date
- B. Day of the week
- C. Action, i.e., type of protest, strike or coercive act
- D. Protester, i.e., group or type
- E. State or protest target

- F. Target or government agent, e.g., police, court, ministry, military, company or organization
- G. Event, a description of the protest or repressive event
- H. Country
- I. Location, the town, city, or region where the event took place; if it was in many cities, then we code it as the whole country
- J. Issue, grievance topic of the protesters or the state
- K. Link date, i.e., a previous date connected to the event that aid understanding, e.g., an anniversary of an historic event, a trial related to an arrest date, an action connected to a previous warning or the imposition of a major change such as martial law
- L. Time, i.e., the time an event occurred, started and stopped if reported; we coded it in 24-hour time (7:00 pm = 19:00)
- M. Number of protesters
- N. Number of protesters arrested
- O. Number of protesters injured
- P. Number of protesters killed
- Q. Property damage (dichotomous—yes or no)
- R. State force involved in the conflict
- S. Number of state force injured
- T. Number of state force killed
- U. Organizational strength of protesters, i.e., probable mobilizable strength based on membership data
- V. Organizational strength of the state (in non-democratic regimes only)—mobilizable police, military, party forces
- V. in democratic states, W. in coercive states: Source of the story
- W. in democratic states, X. in nondemocratic states: Date of story source
- X. in democratic states, Y. in non-democratic states: No event found (coded for days of no reported activity)⁽²⁾

The types of action coded under variable “C” include: accede, adaptation, agreement, appeal, arrest, arson, assassination, assault, attack, beating, blockade, bomb, boycott, break in, cancel, censor, closure, convict, curfew, civil disobedience, commitment, confiscate, confrontation, convoy, coup, declare, demonstration, deployment, deport, destroy, disband, dismiss, disrupt, escape, exit, exclusion, expulsion, extort, extradite, fight, fine, force, general strike, gunfight, harass, hide, hijack, hostage, hunger strike, impeachment, intervention, kneecapping, lockout, march, martial law, mobilization, motorcade, murder, obstruction, occupation, offer, ouster, petition, preclude, preempt, press conference, proscribe, raid, rally, refuse, reject, regime transition, release, repression, resign, riot, robbery, sabotage, search, shooting, slowdown, statement, strike, suicide, support, suspend, symbolic, terror, torture, trespass, trial, ultimatum, unraveling, vandalism, vigil, withdrawal, and withholding. For a brief description of each of these actions please refer to the codebook for European Protest and Coercion Data (2).

The variable “organizational strength” is defined as the “total mobilizable section of the population for each protest organization (or the state)” (2). The research differentiates between democratic countries, for which only dissident organizational strength is estimated, and coercive countries, in which case state organizational strength is added. The general sources to estimate organizational strength include: Europa World Yearbook (1980-1996), International Labor Organization’s annual Yearbook, the World Business Directory, George T. Kurian, ed., World Encyclopedia of Police Forces and Penal Systems, New York: Facts on File, 1989 and

Harry Drost, *What's What and Who's Who in Europe*, New York: Simon and Schuster, 1995. Sources for country-specific data are listed in the codebook for each country (2).

A number of inferential coding conventions were used during the coding process. Since journalists often use terms such as “hundreds” or “hundreds of thousand” instead of definitive numbers, the research team decided to code such terms as “three of whatever unit is described” (2). That means “hundreds” would be coded as 300 and “hundreds of thousand” as 300.000. To signal such an inference the coded number is listed with “1” as its final digit (e.g. 301, 300.001). The same signal is used to indicate if a number is a reporter’s estimate, while the term “almost 5.000” would be coded as 4.999 (2).

If a report indicates injuries but does not specify further than 10 percent of the participants is used as the default number during coding. If the research team encountered a denial of actions such as caused injuries or arrests from authoritarian states, western sources were cross-referenced. If there were two or more authoritative reports in the Western press, the team disregarded the regime's denial (2).

Both general and commercial strikes with support of the population were coded. In the absence of participation numbers, the research team used 10 percent of each local population as a reference number (2).

When coding reported government statistics over a period of time such as “in the last three months, 9,000 left the country”, the team usually chose the 15th of the month as a reference point and then codes 3.000 citizens as exited on the 15th for three months (2).

For a list of country specific acronyms used while coding the data please refer to the codebook for European Protest and Coercion Data.

Sources:

- (1) Francisco, Ron. *European Protest And Coercion Data*.
<https://ronfran.ku.edu/data/index.html>. Last accessed 23.09.2024.
- (2) *Codebook for European Protest and Coercion Data, 1980 through 1995*.
<https://ronfran.ku.edu/data/codebook.txt>. Last accessed 23.09.2024.